

Original Research

The Effect of Corporate Governance on Competitive Advantage Through Organizational Learning

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Abstract

In this rapidly changing environment, organizations need to preserve their competitive position by committing to corporate governance practices and facilitating learning capabilities. This study aims to investigate the influence of corporate governance on competitive advantage through organizational learning at different Jordanian industrial companies listed on the Amman Stock Exchange. In order to evaluate the relationships, a questionnaire with 52 Likert scale items is designed based on previous studies. The questionnaire is distributed randomly to the top and middle managers working at Jordanian industrial companies registered on the Amman Stock Exchange. The collected data are analyzed using multiple linear regression tests along with Baron and Kenney's approach to finding that all factors of corporate governance significantly impact competitive advantage and that organizational learning partially mediates the relationship between corporate governance and competitive advantage. The study can fill the literature gap by exploring the mediating impact of organizational learning on the relationship between corporate governance and competitive advantage.

Keywords: Corporate Governance, Organizational Learning, Competitive Advantage, Jordanian Industrial Companies, Amman Stock Exchange.

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Introduction

In the last few years, competitive advantage has started to occupy the minds of practitioners and academicians to deal with all new global phenomena, such as globalization, integration into the world economy, and openness and liberalization policies. Besides, the fast pace of technological developments urges organizations to find new ways of improving their products. Hence, sell them at competitive prices. Corporate governance looks into ways to enhance the competitive value of organizations. For instance, Eisenhardt (1989) argues that corporate governance practices can lower agency costs, which enhances the financial returns of the firms. He et al., (2009) claimed that corporate governance mechanisms can be used by BOD to encourage competitive actions. Bobillo et al., (2017) found that corporate governance mechanisms foster the firms' innovation practices. Corporate governance is a broad concept that explains how an excellent relationship between the board of directors and shareholders can be established. It includes rules, processes, and policies that can direct the organization to achieve its goals.

The influence of corporate governance on competitive advantage has been studied for decades, but there have been no consensus results. That may be due to the lack of discussion about the variables that affect the relationship between them. Therefore, this study takes into account the mediation effect of organizational learning, including several dimensions explaining this relationship. Organizational learning is the process of creating, retaining, and transferring knowledge within an organization. This study proposes that engaging in corporate governance and organizational learning will influence the organizational competitive advantage, helping it to survive and compete adequately.

This study could provide some contributions to academic research and practical management. Although many articles have investigated the impact of corporate governance on competitive advantage, this study asks whether and how corporate governance impacts competitive advantage. The topic has not yet been fully addressed.

Problem Statement

Rapid changes throughout the world, such as technological development, globalization, and intensive competition, urge organizations to adopt administrative methods that might minimize the negative impact of threats and capture new opportunities. Corporate governance practices can be embraced by organizations to make a difference. Organizations need to start searching for new competitive edges that enable them to stay in the market by using information and communications technology and modern knowledge. The researcher believes that corporate governance along with the practices of organizational learning can be good sources of sustainable competitive advantage. Based on what is mentioned above, this study looks forward to evaluating the influence of corporate governance on competitive advantage through organizational learning by answering the following problem statement.

Does corporate governance impact competitive advantage through organizational learning?

Purpose

This study intends to examine the effect of corporate governance on competitive advantage through organizational learning.

Research Hypotheses

H1: There is a statistically significant effect of corporate governance on competitive advantage.

H2: organizational learning mediates the relationship between corporate governance and competitive advantage.

Literature Review

Corporate Governance and Competitive Advantage

Most theories of corporate governance have only emerged to solve many agency problems, such as competition among managers, profit sharing, and the capital market (Miozzo & Dewick, 2002). Weisbach (1988) found that having outside directors helps in management monitoring. Using Tobin's Q, (Ghabri, 2022) found a direct influential relationship between corporate governance and firm performance by investigating the ability of legal systems to interact with good corporate governance practices. Dkhili Hichem (2023) revealed that environmental, social, and governance (ESG) affect Tobin's Q arguing that ESG is beneficial in terms of firm reputation and image. Raithatha and Haldar (2021) explained that corporate governance might be a source of enhancing corporate financial performance. Natto and M-mokoteli (2022) used GMM Dynamic Panel Data to find a relationship between corporate governance and economic growth of India.

He et al., (2009) conducted a study to explore the relationship between corporate governance and competitive behavior at the firm level. He et al., (2009) assume that corporate governance mechanisms can be applied to monitor the flow of the firm's capabilities and resources and can be used by BOD to encourage competitive actions. Similarly, (Zorn, 2014), in his thesis, proposed that corporate governance mechanisms used by managers and BOD directly affect the competitive actions of the firms. Zoran found that two corporate governance strategies, CEO incentive pay, and CEO equity ownership, are correlated to competitive actions.

Moreover, using a longitudinal research methodology in 6 countries, Bobillo et al., (2017) found that corporate governance mechanisms foster the firms' innovation practices, which assumed a key differentiation strategy of firms. Dzulkifli et al., (2020) analyzed the effect of corporate governance principles on the patients' satisfaction in Happy General Hospital of Makassar City. The results show that independence and fairness principles have a direct relationship with the satisfaction of patients.

Nginyo et al.,(2018) conducted a study using an open-ended items questionnaire to reveal that there is a direct influence of corporate governance on competitive strategies. In their research, corporate governance includes four dimensions: transparency, accountability, fairness, and responsibility.

AL-Qatawneh (2015), in his study, targeted Jordanian Pharmaceutical Companies to find that there is a direct relationship between corporate governance and competitive advantage using a questionnaire. It's found that all dimensions of corporate governance (Accountability, Justice, Social Responsibility, and Autonomy) impact competitive advantage (AL-Qatawneh, 2015).

Based on the above argument, the researcher proposed the first main hypothesis

H₁: Corporate Governance has a significant effect on Competitive Advantage.

Corporate Governance, Organizational Learning, and Competitive Advantage

Lauer and Wilkesmann (2017) argued that positive corporate governance practices can't be productive without the existence of organizational learning. Kruger (2015) found that there is a relationship between corporate governance and organizational learning stressing the importance of applying consistent learning practices in order to use corporate governance practices effectively. Moreover, Nawaiseh et al., (2021) found that corporate governance practices have an impact on organizational learning. In their study, corporate governance including participation, equality, efficiency, strategic vision, transparency and accountability has an influence on organizational learning except for strategic vision and transparency.

In addition, it is important to mention how organizational learning plays an essential role in enhancing the competitive position of organizations. Many previous studies shed light into the effect of organizational learning on competitive advantage. Jashapara (2003) found that the organizational learning system has a positive impact on organizational performance and that the organizational learning focusing on efficiency and proficiency is a reason for competitive advantage in UK construction companies. López et al., (2005) found that organizational learning leads to innovation and competitiveness of firms. Prieto and Revilla (2006) tested 111 firms to show how organizational learning has a relationship between the financial and non-financial performance of the firms.

Moreover, Abadi and Nematizadeh (2012) found that the relationship between corporate governance and strategic planning effectiveness is fostered by organizational learning. They stated: "In conclusion, corporate governance and organizational learning are not only compatible and able to be used in conjunction with one another, but are also complementary. In other words, the effect of a wide learning of organization is possibly to reinforce the effect of corporate governance on strategic planning effectiveness and vice versa".

Regarding the effect of organizational learning on competitive advantage, Gachanja et al., (2020) revealed that organizational learning impacts the innovation output of

industrial firms in Kenya. Chahal and Bakshi, (2015) showed how organizational learning affects intellectual capital which in turn can enhance the competitive advantage of banks.

Based on the research review, there is almost no study explains the mediating role of organizational learning in the relationship between corporate governance and competitive advantage. Despite the dependent and independent variables, several studies found that organizational learning mediates the relationships between variables (e.g., Khaki et al., 2017; (Bahrami et al., 2016; Bai et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2020; Aragón et al., 2014).

Based on the above studies, this study includes the third main hypothesis

H₂: Organizational Learning mediates the relationship between Corporate Governance and Competitive Advantage.

Based on the above discussion, the study model is developed (figure 1)

Figure 1. The study Model

Research Methodology and Findings

Research Instrument

In order to investigate the causal relationships of this study, a quantitative methodology using a questionnaire is adopted. Azim et al., (2015) 28 items are used to evaluate corporate governance. The competitive advantage scale is adopted from Chen and Lai's (2006) with 8 items. Organizational learning is developed by Gomez et al., (2005) with 16 items.

Sampling and Data Collection

The target population of this study includes 1500 middle and top managers working at 47 Jordanian industrial companies listed in Amman Stock Exchange ASE. The sample size is calculated based on the random sampling method with a 95% confidence level. 312 individualized questionnaires were collected, which is enough to represent the study population. Based on the demographic analysis, the males exceed females, which

constitute (59.1%) of the study sample, while Females constitute (40.9%) of the total sample. The age group (36 to 45) ranked first and accounted for 38.8% of the total sample. The next sample is the group aged (27 to 35 years), which forms 36% of the study sample. The age group (46 or Older) comes in third place to constituting 22.8%. finally, the group aged (Under 26 years) represents 2.5% of the total sample. Respondents answered as Supervisors constitute 41.8% of the total sample, followed by the head of the department (37.8%), and managers with 20.3% came in last place. 37.8% of the respondents have (11-15) years of work experience. The next group represents those with 6-10 years of practical experience and constitutes 36.3% of the sample. Respondents with 16 years and above experience represent 23.1%. Finally, those with 5 years and less experience represent 2.8%. The holders of a bachelor's degree constitute 78.8% of this study's total sample, followed by the holders of graduate degrees by 19.7%, and finally, diploma degree holders represent 1.5% of the total sample.

Analysis

Factor Analysis

The principal component analysis with varimax rotation is used to test the exploratory factor analysis for each variable.

Corporate Governance

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test and Bartlett test of sphericity are conducted to verify the sample's sufficiency. The results extracted from the analysis are (KMO=0.939, Bartlett test= 22411.431, df= 378, p=0.000). Factor analysis of corporate governance extracts three components named Commitment to corporate governance, Structure and Functioning of the Board, and Transparency and Disclosure. The three dimensions' cumulative variance is 93.028 % (Table 1).

Table 1. Factor Analysis Results of Corporate Governance

Factor / Item	Factor Loading	Variance (%)	Alpha
Structure and Functioning of the Board		33.137	.989
SFB_15	.863		
SFB_8	.850		
SFB_12	.848		
SFB_7	.844		
SFB_14	.843		
SFB_10	.834		
SFB_9	.829		
SFB_13	.828		
SFB_11	.826		
SFB_16	.819		
Commitment to corporate governance		21.28	.992

Factor / Item	Factor Loading	Variance (%)	Alpha
CG_4	.834		
CG_5	.825		
CG_6	.823		
CG_3	.818		
CG_2	.815		
CG_1	.797		
Transparency and Disclosure		17.208	.993
TD_28	.871		
TD_19	.869		
TD_27	.865		
TD_26	.863		
TD_18	.858		
TD_25	.855		
TD_21	.854		
TD_20	.853		
TD_17	.845		
TD_24	.844		
TD_23	.839		
TD_22	.831		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy			.939
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity		Approx. Chi-Square	22411.431
		df	378
		p-value	.000

Competitive Advantage

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test and Bartlett test of sphericity are conducted to verify the sample's sufficiency. The results extracted from the analysis are (KMO=.928, Bartlett test=6004.684, df=28, p=0.000). Factor analysis test of competitive advantage found only one component named Competitive Advantage with 94.080% as a cumulative variance (Table 2).

Table 2. Factor Analysis Results of Competitive Advantage

Factor / Item	Factor Loading	Variance (%)	Alpha
Competitive Advantage		.967	.991
CA_45	.977		
CA_50	.975		
CA_51	.973		
CA_49	.973		
CA_47	.967		
CA_44	.967		
CA_48	.965		
CA_46	.963		

Factor / Item	Factor Loading	Variance (%)	Alpha
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy			.928
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square		6004.684
	df		28
	p-value		.000

Organizational Learning

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test and Bartlett test of sphericity are conducted to verify the sample's sufficiency. The results extracted from the analysis are (KMO=.896, Bartlett test= 15761.964, df= 120, p=0.000). Factor analysis of organizational learning extracts two components named Managers commitment and openness and System and knowledge perspectives with a cumulative variance of 89.813 % 89.813 % (Table 3).

Table 3. Factor Analysis Results of Organizational Learning

Factor / Item	Factor Loading	Variance (%)	Alpha
Managers Commitment and Openness		49.557	.989
MCO_62	.882		
MCO_61	.874		
MCO_60	.870		
MCO_63	.867		
MCO_53	.834		
MCO_58	.826		
MCO_52	.825		
MCO_55	.816		
MCO_56	.805		
System and knowledge perspectives		40.255	.975
SKP_65	.877		
SKP_64	.864		
SKP_66	.863		
SKP_67	.860		
SKP_57	.736		
SKP_58	.730		
SKP_59	.726		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy			.896
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square		15761.964
	df		120
	p-value		.000

Multiple Regression Analysis

The Effect of Corporate Governance on Competitive Advantage

All regression assumptions were approved to conduct multiple linear regression tests to accept or reject the first hypothesis (Table 4).

Table 4. Multiple Linear Regression of Model 1

Dependent Variable	Independent Variables	β	Std. Error	t-value	p-value	VIF
Competitive Advantage	Commitment to corporate governance	.289	.050	6.256	.000	2.754
	Structure and Functioning of the Board	.326	.054	7.227	.000	2.635
	Transparency and Disclosure	.341	.049	7.660	.000	2.552
$R=.867$ $R^2=.751$ $Adjusted R^2=.749$ $F:323.462$ $p:.000$						

The results indicate that all dimensions of corporate governance (Commitment to Corporate Governance, Structure and Functioning of the Board, and Transparency and Disclosure) have an impact on the competitive advantage ($R=.867$, $R^2=.751$, Adjusted $R^2=.749$, $F(323.462)$, $p:.000$).

Moreover, table 4 shows that the independent variables (Commitment to corporate governance, Structure and Functioning of the Board, and Transparency and Disclosure) explain 75.1% of the variation in the dependent variable (Competitive Advantage). Therefore, the researcher can't reject the first hypothesis of this study

H₁: There is a statistically significant effect of corporate governance (Commitment to Corporate Governance, Structure and Functioning of the Board, and Transparency and Disclosure) on competitive advantage.

The Mediation Effect of Organizational Learning

Managers commitment and openness

In order to test the second hypothesis, Baron & Kenny's (1986) approach is adopted including four steps in which regression analyses are tested. Step 1 is already tested and confirmed (see section 3.3.2.1). Steps 2, 3, and 4 are tested (Tables 5, 6, and 7).

Table 5. Multiple Linear Regression of Model 2

Mediating Variable	Independent Variables	β	Std. Error	t-value	p-value	VIF
Managers commitment and openness	Commitment to corporate governance	.331	.055	6.607	.000	2.754
	Structure and Functioning of the Board	.296	.059	6.056	.000	2.635
	Transparency and Disclosure	.301	.053	6.244	.000	2.552
$R=.842$ $R^2=.708$ $Adjusted R^2=.705$ $F: 259.708$ $p:.000$						

Table 5 shows that all factors of corporate governance (Commitment to Corporate Governance, Structure and Functioning of the Board, and Transparency and Disclosure) impact the mediating variable (Managers Commitment and Openness) ($R=.842$, $R^2=.708$, Adjusted $R^2 = .705$, $F: 259.708$, $p: 0.000$).

Table 6. Multiple Linear Regression of Model 3

Dependent Variable	Independent Variables	β	Std. Error	t-value	p-value
Competitive Advantage	Managers commitment and openness	.870	.026	33.459	.000
$R=.881$ $R^2=.776$ Adjusted $R^2 = .775$ $F: 1119.532$ $p: .000$					

Table 6 shows that managers commitment and openness affects competitive advantage ($R=.881$, $R^2=.776$, Adjusted $R^2 = .775$, $F: 1119.532$, $p: 0.000$).

Table 7. Multiple Linear Regression of Model 4

Dependent Variable	Independent Variables	β	Std. Error	t-value	p-value	VIF
Competitive Advantage	Commitment to Corporate Governance	.117	.044	2.868	.004	3.128
	Structure and Functioning of the Board	.172	.047	4.365	.000	2.936
	Transparency and Disclosure	.184	.043	4.724	.000	2.862
	Managers Commitment and Openness	.521	.042	12.226	.000	3.427
$R=.911$ $R^2=.831$ Adjusted $R^2 = .828$ $F: 392.165$ $p: .000$						

Table 7 shows that all factors of corporate governance (Commitment to Corporate Governance, Structure and Functioning of the Board, and Transparency and Disclosure) along with manager commitment and openness affect competitive advantage ($R=.911$, $R^2=.831$, Adjusted $R^2 = .828$, $F: 392.165$, $p: 0.000$).

To confirm the mediating variable's effect using Baron & Kenney's approach, The Betas' values in the first step are compared with those in the last steps. Table 8 compares Beta values before and after controlling the mediating variable (Managers Commitment and Openness).

Table 8. Betas before and after controlling Managers Commitment and Openness

Independent Variable	Beta Coef before controlling the mediating variable	Significance relationship from the first step	Beta Coef after controlling the mediating variable	Significance relationship from the fourth step	Results
Commitment to corporate governance	.289	Significant	.117	Significant	Partial Mediation
Structure and Functioning of the Board	.326	Significant	.172	Significant	Partial Mediation
Transparency and Disclosure	.341	Significant	.184	Significant	Partial Mediation

Table 8 shows that beta values of all corporate governance dimensions are reduced after controlling the first dimension of the mediating variable (Managers commitment and openness).

System and knowledge perspectives

In order to test the second hypothesis, Baron & Kenny's (1986) approach is adopted including four steps in which regression analyses are tested. Step 1 is already tested and confirmed (see section 3.3.2.1.). Steps 2, 3, and 4 are tested (Tables 9, 10, 11).

Table 9. Multiple Linear Regression of Model 5

Mediating Variable	Independent Variables	β	Std. Error	t-value	p-value	VIF
System and knowledge perspectives	Commitment to corporate governance	.172	.055	3.392	.000	2.754
	Structure and Functioning of the Board	.410	.059	8.293	.000	2.635
	Transparency and Disclosure	.337	.053	6.926	.000	2.552
$R = .838$ $R^2 = .702$ $Adjusted R^2 = .699$ $F: 251.536$ $p: .000$						

Table 9 shows that all factors of corporate governance (Commitment to Corporate Governance, Structure and Functioning of the Board, and Transparency and Disclosure) impact the mediating variable (System and knowledge perspectives) ($R = .838$, $R^2 = .702$, $Adjusted R^2 = .699$, $F: 251.536$, $p: 0.000$)

Table 10. Multiple Linear Regression of Model 6

Dependent Variable	Independent Variables	β	Std. Error	t-value	p-value
Competitive Advantage	System and knowledge perspectives	.899	.025	36.135	.000
$R=.895$ $R^2=.802$ $Adjusted R^2 = .801$ $F: 1305.753$ $p: .000$					

Table 10 shows that System and knowledge perspectives affects competitive advantage ($R=.895$ $R^2=.802$, $Adjusted R^2 = .801$, $F: 1305.753$, $p: 0.000$).

Table 11. Multiple Linear Regression of Model 7

Dependent Variable	Independent Variables	β	Std. Error	t-value	p-value	VIF
Competitive Advantage	Commitment to Corporate Governance	.190	.040	5.205	.000	2.852
	Structure and Functioning of the Board	.090	.046	2.325	.021	3.199
	Transparency and Disclosure	.146	.040	3.946	.000	2.934
	System and knowledge Perspectives	.576	.040	14.573	.000	3.351
$R=.922$ $R^2=.851$ $Adjusted R^2 = .849$ $F: 455.428$ $p: .000$						

Table 11 shows that all factors of corporate governance (Commitment to Corporate Governance, Structure and Functioning of the Board, and Transparency and Disclosure) along with System and knowledge Perspectives affect competitive advantage ($R=.922$, $R^2=.851$, $Adjusted R^2 = .849$, $F: 455.428$, $p: 0.000$).

To test the mediating variable's effect using Baron & Kenney's approach, The Betas' values in the first step are compared with those in the last steps. Table 12 compares Beta values before and after controlling the mediating variable (System and knowledge Perspectives).

Table 12. Betas before and after controlling the System and knowledge perspectives variable

Independent Variable	Beta before controlling the mediating variable	Relationship from the first step	Beta after controlling the mediating variable	Relationship from the fourth step	Results
Commitment to corporate governance	.289	Significant	.190	Significant	Partial Mediation
Structure and Functioning of the Board	.326	Significant	.090	Significant	Partial Mediation
Transparency and Disclosure	.341	Significant	.146	Significant	Partial Mediation

Table 13 shows that beta values of all corporate governance dimensions are reduced after controlling the second dimension of the mediating variable (System and knowledge perspectives).

Conclusion and Implications

Several studies that investigated corporate governance focused on the elements of corporate governance separately and denied the mediation elements that can explain the relationship between corporate governance and competitive advantage. Therefore, this study estimates the impact of corporate governance through the mediation effect of organizational learning that could be involved in any organizational practice.

Regarding the impact of corporate governance on competitive advantage, the results confirm the theoretical and implication studies (He et al., 2009; ZORN, 2014; Dzulkifli et al., 2020; AL-Qatawneh, 2015; Ghabri, 2022; Raithatha and Haldar 2021; Natto and M-mokoteli 2022). Specifically, the study found that all corporate governance elements (commitment to corporate governance, structure and functioning of the board, and transparency and disclosure) significantly impact competitive advantage. The most effective element was transparency and disclosure. That asserts the importance of transparency and disclosure in getting high profits, lowering cost, and enhancing customer satisfaction. Transparent organizations can increase customer satisfaction, enhance their profitability, build good growth, and produce products with competitive cost and high quality.

The second hypothesis claims that organizational learning mediates the impact of corporate governance on competitive advantage. Based on the results of Baron and Kenney (1986), it is found that the first and the second elements of organizational learning (Managers commitment and openness, and System and knowledge perspectives) partially mediate all the relationships between corporate governance dimensions (commitment to corporate governance, structure and functioning of the board, and transparency and disclosure) and competitive advantage. One of the related studies that found close results is “Analyzing the Impact of Corporate Governance and Organizational Learning on Strategic Planning Effectiveness (An Empirical practice among some industrial companies in Iran).” The results of this study found that corporate governance and organizational learning separately have a relationship with strategic planning.

Anyway, this study contributes to the corporate governance study by explicating the mediating role of organizational learning. It can be a good reference for Jordanian manufacturing organizations as it is one of the first to examine the mediating effect of organizational learning on the relationship between corporate governance and competitive advantage.

Regarding the managerial implications, the study approves that corporate governance includes vital capabilities that influence competitive advantage, which is considered an important measure of organizational performance. By committing to corporate governance, organizations can build morale and a good reputation that helps build strong relationships. Corporate governance requires organizations to comply with local, national, and international policies and regulations, and thus reducing the likelihood of

costly crises and scandals. Moreover, by being committed to corporate governance practices, having the best structure of the board, and disclosing transparent information, organizations can enhance their competitive positions in the markets.

Moreover, the study emphasizes the importance of organizational learning in explaining and supporting the effect of corporate governance on competitive advantage. Management in organizations needs to encourage organizational learning practices along with the practices of corporate governance for greater competitive advantage. When corporate governance and organizational learning are applied jointly in a proper way, organizations can be more competitive. Organizational learning that dedicates time and resources to building a learning culture makes organizations more competitive.

Future Research and Limitation

The study provides researchers with several points of view to study. Researchers can include various control variables to explain the relationships between corporate governance and competitive advantage. For example, intellectual capital, information technology, strategic position, customer satisfaction, and reputation are important control variables that might facilitate the relationship.

Moreover, the population sample is limited to Jordanian manufacturing companies. Researchers can repeat investigating the same relationships in several sectors and various countries. In addition, a larger sample can be studied.

Further research could be conducted by applying the topic in a case study. A case study could deeply explain the interaction between variables. By monitoring firm parameters, researchers can evaluate the variables and their determinants using a qualitative method. The case study can specifically explain how corporate governance can be applied in manufacturing companies.

In spite of the study's results, it contains limitations. The study is cross-sectional, focusing on a specific point of time. The study could be conducted using panel data where the study's variables are compared in different time periods. Moreover, the corporate governance questionnaire including some items is not compared with external governance models. The instrument of data collection is restricted to some factors where researchers can adopt different instruments to evaluate the relationships of this study.

Author Contributions

Raghad Darweesh verified and contributed to the data analysis and, took over most of data interpretation and writing of the manuscript, liaised with co-authors regarding any editorial queries, agreed to take responsibility and be accountable for the contents of the article.

Mohammad Abuareish made a significant contribution to the work reported. Specifically, in the conception, study design, execution, acquisition of data, analysis and interpretation. He also critically reviewed the article.

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